

Efforts To Improve the Economy of Village Communities Through the Development of BUM Desa

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the formulation of policy changes in efforts to improve the economy of rural communities through a study of Environmental Strengths, External & Internal Demands, Interaction & Structural Strengths within organizations, Role Strategy Formulation, Programs, considering available resources, and to obtain alternative recommendations for problem-solving based on changes in resources. Policy formulation is the most vital stage in the public policy process, as all stages depend on how policymakers formulate policies. Policy formulation requires analysis to solve problems from several alternative solutions obtained from the SWOT analysis (*Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats*) conducted through data collection. The data analysis tool used in this study is the interactive data analysis technique, using a qualitative descriptive approach to interpret the data obtained through SWOT analysis through interviews, observations, and document studies. The results of this study indicate that BUM Desa Sukses Makmur (Village-Owned Enterprise) possesses significant internal strengths, including management performance, business diversification, experience in collaboration, clear legal status, and support from the government and community, which serve as strong assets. However, the BUM Desa (Village-Owned Enterprise) also faces internal weaknesses such as limited human resources, stagnant management in the past, reporting challenges, potential overlapping tasks, leader dependency, insufficient collaboration, and unstable human resources. Externally, there are significant opportunities in the development of marketing for MSMEs and village products, the need for MSMEs to have a platform and training, improving the management of natural resources, the potential of human resources in agriculture and livestock, cooperation with local companies, and positive trends in local economic empowerment. Several external threats include price fluctuations, business competition, regulatory changes, changes in consumer preferences, limited sustainable support, and the risk of bad credit. For sustainable development, BUM Desa Sukses Makmur is recommended to strengthen governance, develop human resources, focus on flagship business units based on local potential and food security, strengthen collaboration, diversify capital, empower the community, and increase active participation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

According to Law Number 3 of 2024, the second amendment to Law Number 6 of 2014, a village is defined as a legal community with specific territorial boundaries. Villages, which also include traditional villages or other recognized terms, have the authority to regulate and manage governmental affairs and the interests of the local community based on community initiatives, customary rights, and/or traditional rights recognized and respected within the

framework of the unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia.

The administration of a village is carried out by a government known as the village government. Additionally, the management of the village's economy is conducted not only by the village government but also by business entities established by the village government in collaboration with the village community through the Village Assembly (MUSDES), known as the Village-Owned Enterprise (BUM Desa). These entities are formed based on the Village

Assembly (MUSDES) agreement. The MUSDES (Village Assembly) agreed upon the objectives and vision-mission.

From the data above, it can be seen that the distribution of BUM Desa across Indonesia has spread to all regions, compared to the total number of villages in Indonesia, which is 82,395, as obtained from (Central Statistics Agency, 2024), and the average number of BUM Desa that have been established has also partially obtained legal status.

The government is currently prioritizing the management of BUM Desa as a key program. Therefore, village governments, BUM Desa managers, and policymakers should also respond to this initiative. They should demonstrate seriousness in managing BUM Desa, particularly in establishment, policy formulation, or developing new approaches for existing BUM Desa. Pasuruan Regency possesses various aspects that can support the development of BUM Desa in each village, given its geographical conditions and existing human and natural resources. As cited by the researcher from the Pasuruan Regency website (Pasuruankab, 2024), the potential and conditions of Pasuruan Regency include its geographical location along the strategic economic corridor of Surabaya-Jember/Banyuwangi/Bali, Surabaya-Malang, and Malang-Jember/Banyuwangi/Bali, which provides significant economic value. The presence of the Gempol-Pandaan toll road and the ongoing construction of the Gempol-Pasuruan toll road further enhance Pasuruan Regency as an attractive location for manufacturing investment development.

Additionally, Pasuruan Regency possesses abundant potential in various areas, including tourism, industrial zones, small-scale industries, agricultural commodities, and natural resources. These opportunities can be leveraged by local leaders in the villages, particularly through collaboration with stakeholders in industrial zones, small-scale industries, agricultural commodities, and the utilization of tourism and natural resources in various villages to manage these resources collectively with the villages and maximize their potential to enhance the local economy. (Pasuruan Regency Government, 2024) The objectives of this study are to understand how BUM Desa policy formulation is implemented in efforts to improve the economy of the village community in Wonosari Village, Tuter Sub-district, Pasuruan District, and to identify the factors influencing the formulation of BUM Desa policies in efforts to enhance the local economy in the successful BUM Desa Sukses Makmur in Wonosari Village, Tuter District, Pasuruan Regency.

Research Benefits, Theoretical benefits: Theoretically, to contribute to academic knowledge, particularly in the field of public administration related to public policy studies, specifically regarding the formulation of BUM Desa policies. Practical Benefits: This study is expected to broaden the researchers' knowledge, particularly in the field of Public Policy with a focus on BUM Desa Policy

Formulation, by applying the theories that have been studied. Thus, this study is expected to enhance the researchers' understanding within the scope of Public Administration studies. This research is expected to present concrete solutions in the form of Policy Briefs and serve as guidance for all stakeholders at the village level and within the scope of BUM Desa. This guidance is expected to be helpful in the policy formulation process and the management of BUM Desa governance. The general public, this research is expected to provide significant benefits to the broader community by providing comprehensive knowledge on various aspects of BUM Desa. Additionally, this research aims to foster public interest in actively participating in all stages of BUM Desa policy, from formulation and implementation to evaluation, in their respective villages.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Public policy, in essence, is a decision made by government institutions or officials to regulate community life to achieve welfare. Public policy is expected to provide solutions to various problems the community faces. Keban (2004:55) in (2015) explains that “Public Policy” can be viewed as a philosophical concept, as a product, as a process, and as a framework. As a philosophical concept, policy is a set of principles or desired conditions; as a product, policy is seen as a series of conclusions or recommendations; and as a process, policy is seen as a way through which an organization can know what is expected of it, namely, programs and mechanisms for achieving its products. As a framework, policy is a process of bargaining and negotiation to formulate issues and methods of implementation.

R. Dye provides a basic definition of public policy: "Public policy is whatever governments choose to do or not to do" (Kadji, 2015), Meanwhile, according to Carl Friedrich in (Sadhana, 2011), he states that: "Policy is an action aimed at achieving a proposed goal by an individual, group, or government in a specific environment, in the face of certain obstacles, while seeking opportunities to achieve the desired goal or objective."

Public policy will eventually lead to the implementation process. Policy implementation is an important stage in the policy process because it is through implementation that the impacts or benefits of the implemented policy will be known. Theory of Public Policy Formulation, Policy formulation is the most vital stage in the public policy process, because all stages in public policy depend on how policymakers formulate or draft a policy. As stated by Thomas R. Dye (1995)", policy formulation is the government's effort to take action on public life to solve problems that arise in society. Because the government has authoritative power, its interventions can compel the public. However, in reality, this authority produces public policy, which is sometimes created solely to support the interests of specific groups or factions. According to Dunn (2000), several methods of public policy

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analysis are presented that are very helpful in formulating public policy, including: (1) Problem formulation, (2) Forecasting, (3) Recommendations, (4) Monitoring, and (5) Evaluation. According to him, problem formulation, forecasting, and recommendations are the methods used in the policy formulation process. According to Sadhana (2011), citing William Dunn's thoughts, problem formulation helps to

identify the problems to be solved; forecasting helps to produce policy formulations or expected outcomes; and recommendations help to facilitate policy adoption and formulation.

In this context, the entire process can be illustrated in the following diagram:

Image 1. Three's Policy Formulation Model Descriptive Model

Source: According to Paine and Naumes in (Kadji, 2015)

In several policy formulation models according to some experts, researchers focus more on the model that researchers will use, because in this model, according to researchers, it is in line with what has been regulated in Government Regulation Number 11 of 2021 concerning Village-Owned Enterprises (BUM Desa), which will later become the focus of this study, which outlines the mechanisms for policy formulation in BUM Desa, including the role of the community in the policy formulation process and the adjustment of policy changes within BUM Desa, through the Village Assembly (Musyawarah Desa) or commonly referred to as MUSDES. According to Pained and Naumes in "The Policy Formulation Model", the researcher suggests that it is suitable to examine how policy formulation occurs in BUM Desa and how to analyze it in BUM Desa.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1 Research Approach

This study employs a qualitative method with a descriptive approach to obtain accurate information regarding aspects related to BUM Desa. In this study, the researcher explores information and facts regarding the formulation of BUM Desa policies to improve the village community's economy at the successful BUM Desa Sukses Makmur in

Wonosari Village, Tatur District, Pasuruan Regency.

3.2 Research Location

This study was conducted at the BUM Desa "Sukses Makmur" in Wonosari Village, Tatur District, Pasuruan Regency. The research location was selected based on the consideration that the Sukses Makmur Village-Owned Enterprise in Wonosari Village has been classified as an advanced Village-Owned Enterprise (BUM Desa) by the regency. The selection of this location was based on selecting a BUM Desa that has been established for a long time, as well as selecting a BUM Desa with a very different geographical location and a significantly different level of economic development.

3.3 Research Analysis

The researcher used SWOT analysis in the data collection process, which includes the following components: SWOT analysis. This data analysis aims to organize data systematically to understand the research results. In this data analysis stage, the researcher will process the data collected from the field and the SWOT analysis conducted during the data collection process. The data will then be generalized and processed to produce the research results.

IV. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Wonosari Village is one of 12 villages in the administrative area of Tukur District, Pasuruan Regency. According to the elders of Wonosari Village, the village was established during the Pasuruan Regency administration led by Raden Untung Suropati. At that time, people were *clearing land* or searching for residential and agricultural land by cutting down forests. The Village-Owned Enterprise "Sukses Makmur" is a Wonosari Village, Tukur Sub-district business entity. The Village-Owned Enterprise was established in 2014 under the name Sukses Makmur, legally recognized by Village Regulation No. 5 of 2014 on Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDesa), which was later amended by Village Regulation No. 6 of 2016.

4.1 Environmental Strengths, External & Internal Demands,

Through the results of a Focus Group Discussion conducted by the researcher with several representatives of BUM Desa Wonosari stakeholders, attended by Mr. Bayu as the Director of BUM Desa, Mrs. Eli as the Treasurer, and several heads of BUM Desa business units, as well as community representatives from the private sector entrepreneurs within the Wonosari Village area, as well as several representatives from the farmer and plantation sectors, and several representatives from the retail business sector in the Wonosari Village Market, regarding the requests from the community that the researcher gathered, including those conveyed by the representative of the Village Council (BPD) and BUM Desa Supervisor, Mr. Gilang, who stated,

"Here is the thing: the farmers' group here has been unable to proceed, and the village has been like this for a long time. The fertilizer subsidy has not been distributed yet. If the BUM Desa can provide the subsidized fertilizer according to the plan, it would be helpful because the fertilizer we buy from the market is expensive and we cannot afford it. If the village-owned enterprise can provide the subsidized fertilizer, the villagers who have flower gardens could collaborate with the village-owned enterprise to market their flowers collectively, benefiting all the villagers who have flower gardens. Flowers are profitable if we can collaborate and find a reliable collector who can consistently buy the harvest, like in the local market."

From the presentation, researchers can see that farmers and gardeners desire subsidized fertilizer with controlled prices, as farming groups in the village have not yet resumed operations after a prolonged hiatus. Farmers and planters hope that the Village-Owned Enterprise (BUM Desa) can contribute to preparing for the sale of subsidized fertilizer. Additionally, planters also expressed their hope for creating integrated marketing facilities for flower planters, aiming to increase their visibility outside the region and assist in sales and promotions outside the area.

Additionally, statements were also made by the BPD representative, Mr. Ali Muda, who stated,

"Many of our residents are small business owners, Mr. and Mrs. Some make food, some make toys, some make headscarves, mats, and some sell flower bouquets and other items. These people have a great passion to develop their businesses, but the challenges they often face are related to marketing and financial management."

From Mr. Ali Muda's statement, researchers can also see that UMK & UMKM entrepreneurs also desire a platform to accommodate them and provide them with opportunities to grow through online marketing and financial management training for their UMKM businesses. The village of Wonosari has human resources in income or employment, including farmers, who number approximately 203 people in Wonosari. They are farmers and planters; on average, they have their fields and plantations. In addition to farmers and planters, the residents of Wonosari Village also have many professions, such as livestock farmers, with approximately 220 people engaged in this sector, including cattle farmers, goat farmers, chicken farmers, and duck farmers. Additionally, some work as traders and small-scale entrepreneurs (SMEs) who utilize the agricultural products and livestock raised by the farmers, plantation workers, and livestock farmers.

Furthermore, according to research findings, many traders in markets outside the Tukur sub-district, including residents of Wonosari Village, engage in trade outside the village to sell their agricultural and plantation products. This was also confirmed by the Village Head of Wonosari when asked by the researcher. The capabilities of BUM Desa Sukses Makmur have earned it the title of Best BUM Desa in Pasuruan Regency, awarded based on the ranking of BUM Desa based on sound management, conducted by the Pasuruan Regency Community Empowerment Agency in 2020. It also had the opportunity to represent Pasuruan Regency in a presentation on BUM Desa management. It was awarded the 2nd Category for Community Development and Engagement in the BUM Desa Award 2020, organized by the East Java Provincial Government. In 2020, the BUM Desa also received an award from the Pasuruan Regency Government, through the Regent at the time, Mr. Irsyad Yusuf, M.M. This was obtained by researchers through observation and clarified by Mr. Bayu in an interview.

"The BUM Desa previously received awards from the province and the regency. At the regency level, it won the award for best BUM Desa management in 2020 through a ranking conducted by the DPMD based on reports and activities. Then, after winning at the district level, the Regent instructed them to represent the district at the provincial level to present on BUM Desa management during the BUM Desa Award 2020 event at ITS Surabaya. Alhamdulillah, they also won an award; if I'm not mistaken, it was the second prize. You can check the certificate later."

4.2 Discussion

Policy formulation is the most critical stage in the public policy process, as all subsequent stages depend on how policymakers formulate or develop a policy. According to Dunn (2000) in Sadhana (2011), several methods of public policy analysis that are very useful in formulating public policy include problem formulation, forecasting, recommendations, monitoring, and evaluation. However, according to him, only problem formulation, forecasting, and recommendations are directly used in the policy formulation. According to Sadhana (2011), considering William Dunn's theory, it is clear that problem formulation aims to identify the problems that need to be solved. Forecasting also helps predict the expected impact or formulation of policies. Finally, recommendations contribute to adopting policies and the policy formulation itself.

Therefore, to produce a good policy formulation, conducting an in-depth study of an issue is necessary. Several stages are needed to identify the problem to be discussed and become a policy formulation or recommendation. This is in line with Paine and Naumes' theory (in Kadji, 2015), which developed the ideas of Ripley and David Easton, describing the policy formulation model as a constantly changing interaction between policy actors and their environment. This is considered a real, open, and constantly changing interaction between policy actors and their environment. Inputs and outputs are generated from this interaction, and the outputs produced by the organization ultimately become an important part of the environment. Furthermore, the environment interacts with the organization and produces actions that can impact the organization. Dynamic policy changes begin with

changes in the organizational environment, which necessitate adjustments to the dynamics of change in the environment by reviewing the problems and obstacles faced by the organization.

Policy change, according to Hall (Dudley & Richardson, 2000), in (Dwiyanto, 2017), is characterized by a dominant paradigm shift. The paradigm of a policy-making actor and the dynamic resource environment, or policy formulation, significantly influence how a particular policy is formulated and to what extent it can be implemented.

Therefore, in the policy formulation process, it is necessary to obtain alternative solutions to problems to refine and obtain reasonable solutions. This requires using SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats). SWOT analysis is a comprehensive framework for evaluating the strategic position of BUM Desa Sukses Makmur. In SWOT analysis, it is important to carefully identify the internal and external aspects that influence the existence and sustainability of BUM Desa Sukses Makmur and the process of environmental change in BUM Desa Sukses Makmur. Overall, identifying external opportunities and threats provides a deep understanding of the operational context and potential risks BUM Desa Sukses Makmur faces. A deep understanding of external elements enables the formulation of more appropriate strategic decisions and ensures their relevance in the long term. Policies or strategies based on considering opportunities will drive growth and innovation. In contrast, policies or strategies based on considering threats will enhance the resilience and adaptability of BUM Desa in the long term and dynamic environmental conditions.

Table SWOT Analysis of Internal and External Aspects in BUM Desa

INTERNAL ASPECTS	
<i>Strengths</i>	<i>Weaknesses</i>
Performance of BUM Desa Management at the District Level during the period (2019-2020) Diversification of Existing Business Units Experience in Cooperation with Financial Institutions and Third Parties Legal Status of the Successful Makmur Village-Owned Enterprise Support from the Village and Regional Government Support and Active Participation from the Community Efforts for Improvement and Development in the Current Period, through	Initial Challenges in Establishment Related to Human Resource Competencies in the Successful and Prosperous Village-Owned Enterprise There was a Period of Stagnation in Management from 2022 to 2024 Limited Activity Reporting in the (2022-2023) Annual Report Potential Overlap of Roles and Positions within the Organizational Structure Reliance on Leadership Figures and Leadership Style Across Different Periods Inadequate Utilization of Potential for Collaboration with Local Companies Instability of internal management of human resources

EXTERNAL ASPECTS	
<i>Opportunities</i>	<i>Threats</i>
Potential for Integrated Marketing Development for MSMEs, Farmers, and Planters Need for Platforms and Training for Local SMEs in Wonosari Village Potential for improving the management of village-owned enterprises (BUM Desa) through the utilization of abundant and diverse natural resources Significant Human Resource Potential in the Agriculture, Plantation, and Livestock Sectors Potential for Collaboration with Local Companies in the Tukur Subdistrict Area, Previous Collaboration Experience as a Foundation Positive trends regarding the utilization of BUM Desa for local economic empowerment and improving the economy within the community	Market price fluctuations and agricultural commodities, Competitive Threats from Other Business Actors, Especially Larger-Scale Operators in Potential Sectors Unfavorable Regulatory Changes, Changes in Consumer Preferences and Tastes and Potential Loss of Public Trust Limited sustainable support from local companies, Limited Access to Information and Technology, Risk of Non-Performing Loans in Savings and Loan Units, and Non-Performing Loans in Market Fees in Village Market Units

Based on the data in the table above and the data obtained, **the Strength Analysis of** the Successful and Prosperous Village-Owned Enterprise (BUM Desa) identifies several significant strengths that serve as important capital for future development and policy formulation, including; Achievements in the management of BUM Desa at the district level during the period 2019-2020, receiving the title of Best BUM Desa in Pasuruan District in 2020 and winning second place in the 2020 BUM Desa Awards at the East Java Provincial level, demonstrate that the previous management of BUM Desa was successful and innovative. This recognition provides substantial BUM Desa with social capital and legitimacy. Diversification of Operational Units: The BUM Desa currently manages various operational units, including a village market, a laundry service, a clean water supplier, a field manager, a savings and loan service, a waste management service, and a stationery and photocopy shop. This diversification demonstrates the BUM Desa's ability to meet diverse community needs and generate multiple income sources, enhancing financial stability. With experience collaborating with financial institutions and third parties, BUM Desa has collaborated with commercial banks such as BNI and BRI and third parties like BPJS and PT. Pos Indonesia. This experience demonstrates that BUM Desa can develop services and business units by collaborating and leveraging external networks. Even though previous collaborations were temporarily halted, these experiences provide valuable lessons and open opportunities for better collaboration in the future.

4.3 The Strength of Interaction and Structure within the Institutional Organization of the Successful BUM Desa

The organizational structure of BUM Desa Sukses Makmur, as stipulated in Wonosari Village Regulation No. 6 of 2016 on BUM Desa, conceptually possesses significant potential

strengths in terms of interaction and governance within the BUM Desa institutional framework. These include the Village Assembly (Musyawarah Desa), which serves as the highest decision-making forum regarding the establishment, management, capital allocation, the Articles of Association and Bylaws, and the development of BUM Desa. This forum is decisive in formulating BUM Desa policies for future development by implementing strong participatory mechanisms involving various village elements, including the BUM Desa structure, the private sector, and *civil society*. By fostering interaction among these sectors based on Village Assembly decisions, conducted inclusively and transparently, this forms a solid foundation for the sustainability and development of BUM Desa. However, its effectiveness heavily depends on the quality of dialogue, fair representation, and concrete follow-up actions from the assembly outcomes. The strategic role of the village head as an advisor/commissioner provides the potential to maintain the full role of the village government in safeguarding and protecting BUM Desa as a business sector under the village. BUM Desa can also utilize this to collaborate with the private sector and companies to establish new business units and assist in developing and improving the village economy by building an economic cycle at the village level.

Additionally, the role of the supervisors, namely the Village Council (BPD), is to implement control mechanisms and channel community aspirations to meet community needs, whether in terms of goods/services or employment opportunities for the community. Equally important is the proactive mandate of operational managers (BUM Desa administrators), who serve as the driving force in implementing, developing, exploring potential, and collaborating to build a prosperous BUM Desa that can positively impact the economic cycle at the village level. This

is further emphasized in Permendes PD TT No. 3 of 2021, which represents the community in monitoring performance and providing input, serving as a crucial mechanism for control and channeling aspirations related to the needs for goods/services and employment opportunities for the community.

Additionally, the interactions within the organizational structure of successful and prosperous village-owned enterprises (BUM Desa) require transformation and adaptation of regulations to align with government policies at both the regional and national levels regarding BUM Desa and their related matters, such as the policy outlined in Permendes PD TT No. 3 of 2025, which regulates the Guidelines for the Use of Village Funds (DD) for Food Security in Support of Food Self-Sufficiency. This regulation serves as a guideline for villages to utilize Village Funds to support food security and self-sufficiency programs, which the Village Government must implement in collaboration with BUM Desa.

4.4 Formulation of Strategies and Programs for the Development of Successful and Prosperous BUM Desa through Consideration of Resources

Successful and Prosperous Village-Owned Enterprises (BUM Desa) have significant potential supported by a clear organizational structure, a strong legal foundation, abundant natural and human resources, and government and community support. However, challenges such as instability in human resource management, periods of past management stagnation, limited access to capital, and the suboptimal utilization of local and external market opportunities hinder significant progress for BUM Desa.

According to Sujarwoto (2020), in Miftakhul, Laily, Setyowati, and Hayat (2024), public policy must always be able to adapt to changes and the dynamics of the resource environment. Due to this, public policy is not merely an understanding of the existing system. It must address two issues: how to create public policy with fairness and how to create public policy that can overcome future challenges. The new regulations, such as Permendes PD TT No. 3 of 2021 and PP No. 11 of 2021, provide a more comprehensive framework and opportunities for institutional strengthening and the development of BUM Desa businesses. Additionally, Permendes PD TT No. 3 of 2025 specifically directs the use of Village Funds for food security, which can become a strategic focus for BUM Desa Sukses Makmur with its agricultural and livestock potential. Therefore, strategic and targeted policy development is needed to address internal weaknesses, leverage internal strengths and existing opportunities in line with the new regulatory context, and mitigate risks, with the primary objective of improving the economy of Wonosari Village.

The *first* strategy is to leverage the highly favorable conditions for BUM Desa. By leveraging the internal strengths of BUM Desa and existing opportunities, the

strategy to be implemented in this situation is to support an aggressive *growth-oriented strategy*. Optimizing the Potential of Natural and Human Resources Through the Development of Priority Business Units, utilizing the diversity of natural resources (flower farming, livestock farming, nature tourism) and the potential of human resources in entrepreneurship by developing relevant business units. For example, BUM Desa can act as aggregators and marketers for village-specific products (flowers, processed milk), develop nature-based tourism packages, or provide infrastructure and facilities to support these sectors. Strengthening Strategic Partnerships with Local Companies and Third Parties for Market Expansion and Services, leveraging previous collaboration experience and strong legal status to establish more strategic partnerships with companies in Tatur Sub-district (agro-frozen food, horticulture, and tourism) to expand the market reach of village products or provide supporting services. Collaboration with financial institutions (banks, fintech) can help address capital constraints by leveraging the performance of existing business units as a draw and empowering Local MSMEs Through Digital Platforms and Business Incubation, focusing on nurturing local MSMEs and combining the potential of entrepreneurial human resources with mini-market development plans. Village-owned enterprises can create digital platforms to market MSME products and organize business incubation programs, including financial management training, access to capital, and digital marketing training. Development of Ecotourism Based on Natural and Local Cultural Potential: Utilize natural tourism potential, such as waterfalls and hills, and combine it with cultural potential and local products. BUM Desa can increase village income and create jobs by managing tourist attractions, providing tour packages, or collaborating with tourism-aware groups.

The *second* strategy is to leverage internal strengths to reduce the likelihood of risks. Even though BUM Desa Sukses Makmur faces various threats, it still has internal strengths. BUM Desa must leverage its internal strengths to capitalize on long-term opportunities through product or market diversification. In other words, BUM Desa must expand the types of products or services it offers and reach new or different market segments from those it currently serves. BUM Desa should utilize local strengths for business unit diversification to reduce competition and market variation risks. With its natural resources (SDA) and human resources (SDM), BUM Desa can continue to develop various business units that are not dependent on the same market. This reduces the risk of fluctuations in the prices of certain commodities or competition in a single sector, such as the agricultural sector, plantation sector, and horticulture sector. Strengthening institutions and good governance to increase trust and reduce potential conflicts, BUM Desa can build strong stakeholder trust and reduce the possibility of conflicts

of interest by strengthening and improving clear organizational structures, transparent reporting, and adequate supervision involving BPD and community participation and improving service quality and product innovation based on village potential to maintain competitiveness, leveraging knowledge of local potential to develop unique and high-quality products and services, thereby gaining a competitive edge over competitors. It is important to encourage sustainable innovation. Building extensive cooperation networks to anticipate regulatory changes and secure markets by collaborating with various parties (other village-owned enterprises, local governments, village-owned enterprise associations, and BUM DESMA) to expand market networks and obtain the latest information on regulatory changes.

The *third* strategy is to minimize internal weaknesses and overcome internal problems of BUM Desa by taking advantage of existing opportunities. In this situation, BUM Desa faces a huge opportunity. However, it also faces several internal constraints or weaknesses. Enhancing the capacity of human resources (HR) managers in a structured and sustainable manner with government support and opportunities for collaboration with universities or consultants to address HR weaknesses through comprehensive and sustainable training programs covering modern BUM Desa management, financial management, marketing, and the development of specific business units such as horticultural agribusiness and tourism. Focus on maintaining and improving leadership quality from a leader and human resources from managers or operational staff to address instability in BUM Desa. Building a transparent and accountable governance system with the support of technology utilization to address weaknesses in reporting potential job overlaps by implementing information systems and technology to manage financial, operational, and reporting processes integrated into a digital management information system. Follow up on the restructuring of the Sukses Makmur Village-Owned Enterprise (BUM Desa) that has been carried out with clear and professional task distribution, by evaluating the previous period of stagnation, by clearly defining job descriptions for each position and effective communication channels within the BUM Desa organization by reviewing existing village regulations by Government Regulation No. 11 of 2021 regarding the regulation of job descriptions and effective communication channels, and if necessary, involving experts to translate and develop optimal workflows and structures within the BUM Desa to improve performance within the Sukses Makmur BUM Desa organization. Building diversified access to capital, not only relying on Village Funds, BUM Desa needs to actively seek alternative sources of capital through cooperation with financial institutions, leveraging the good performance of BUM Desa and clear assets, or even through investment schemes involving the community or private sector based on mutually beneficial principles, by

Government Regulation No. 11 of 2021 and Ministry of Village, Development, and Transmigration Regulation No. 3 of 2021, and reinforced by Village Regulations that clearly outline guidelines and serve as a strong foundation for BUM Desa.

The *fourth* strategy is to minimize BUM Desa's internal weaknesses and avoid external risks. In this situation, BUM Desa faces a highly unfavorable condition: various threats and internal weaknesses. However, these two aspects can be used as insights and experience to maintain the sustainability of BUM Desa in taking further actions, or what can be called a defensive strategy, or maintaining sustainability in all matters related to the prosperous BUM Desa. Prioritizing the stabilization of human resources (HR) managers in BUM Desa and improving internal capacity, with a primary focus on overcoming HR instability in BUM Desa through transparent and competency-based recruitment, career development programs, and improving the welfare of managers, as well as building a positive organizational culture. Developing contingency plans to anticipate capital risks, given the limited capital available in BUM Desa, necessitates having backup plans and alternative strategies to ensure operational sustainability within BUM Desa and evaluating and restructuring ineffective or high-risk business units by conducting a comprehensive review and evaluation of the performance of each existing business unit. If business units continue to incur losses or pose a high risk to the sustainability of BUM Desa, restructuring or even closing these business units is highly likely to avoid greater losses. Building effective and transparent communication with the community and relevant stakeholders, such as establishing open and honest communication with the community, village government, Village Council (BPD), and related partners to build mutual understanding, gain support, and reduce the potential for conflicts. The above strategies are designed to complement each other and must be implemented in an integrated manner. The success and suitability of their implementation will significantly depend on the commitment of all elements within BUM Desa Sukses Makmur and the support of all relevant stakeholders in Wonosari Village.

4.5 Alternative Policy Recommendations for the Development of BUM Desa Sukses Makmur

Based on the results of the analysis conducted in identifying internal and external aspects of the BUM Desa, as well as considering the strength of interactions and organizational structure within the BUM Desa, and the formulation of strategies and programs for BUM Desa development through resource considerations, the following policy recommendations for the development of BUM Desa Sukses Makmur can be presented:

Strengthening adaptive and participatory institutional governance. The Village Government and the Village Council (BPD) together with BUM Desa can immediately hold a consultation meeting involving community leaders and

experts to review existing Village Regulations and align them with Government Regulation No. 11 of 2021 on Village-Owned Enterprises and Ministerial Regulation No. 3 of 2021 on Joint Village-Owned Enterprises for further discussion, moreover, specifically for strengthening the institutional governance of BUM Desa and following up on recommendations for policy changes to develop a prosperous BUM Desa based on existing local resources.

The implementation will be carried out through village meetings involving relevant stakeholders in BUM Desa, and a transparent and focused schedule with specific themes for discussion will be established in a phased manner, strengthening transparent, accountable, and efficient financial management. BUM Desa can adopt an application-based accounting system, or BUM Desa can also collaborate with a team of experts to create an accounting system, which will be accompanied by intensive training for financial managers in BUM Desa on the application-based digital accounting system. to ensure accountability and transparency through well-structured reporting outputs from digital applications, presented in financial statements in a format easily understood by the entire community.

The outputs can then be used for routine evaluations in BUM Desa and village meetings. They can also be accessed or published through village notice boards or village websites to ensure transparency to the general public. The implementation involves developing a digital accounting system application for BUM Desa, conducting scheduled training to support the application system, and scheduling regular reporting through village schedules (Village Assembly) or print and digital publications to the public.

Strategic Investment in the Development of Competent and Integrity-Driven Human Resources. Formulating a medium-term human resource development plan with a 3 to 5-year timeframe. This plan can specifically identify the competency requirements for each managerial position within the BUM Desa structure, including a deep understanding of the ideology of BUM Desa and the principles of effective collaboration by Government Regulation No. 11 of 2021 on Village-Owned Enterprises.

Continuous training programs can be specifically budgeted annually and implemented through collaboration with certified institutions, public or private universities, and involving experts from the private sector and civil society organizations. The training materials should at least cover several aspects that are essential for BUM Desa, including aspects of BUM Desa management in modern governance, financial management, digital marketing, management of specific business units including food security as regulated in Permendes No. 3 of 2025 concerning Guidelines for the Use of Village Funds (DD) for Food Security in Support of Food Self-Sufficiency and to be implemented in BUM Desa, as well as the development of collaborative leadership skills and conflict management. An open and competency-based system

can be applied to potential managers in the recruitment process. Additionally, a transparent and fair Performance-Based Remuneration and Incentive System can be developed and socialized, along with clear Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for each unit within the BUM Desa organization.

The implementation may involve representatives from various sectors in the manager selection team through appointment at the Village Assembly, and training programs may also be explicitly designed to build a comprehensive understanding of the objectives and values of BUM Desa among managers. Development of Priority Business Units Based on Local Potential and Sustainable Food Security. The development of business units in the form of utilizing local potential, such as involving MSMEs, farmers, and cattle breeders in the Wonosari Village area, with a primary focus on supporting food security and meeting agricultural and plantation needs, as well as establishing a marketing center for local agricultural and plantation products. Examples of business units that can be considered include crop management involving local SMEs to increase added value, food storage development with active farmer participation, or providing agricultural needs through collaboration with other village-owned enterprises (BUM Desa).

Additionally, establishing an integrated marketing center for agricultural, livestock, and local SME products is feasible through forming a dairy processing unit that could produce locally branded dairy products under the Wonosari Village name. Additionally, tourism processing business units can be established by utilizing the existing natural resources (SDA) in the village, involving youth groups or community organizations to collaborate in creating tourism sector business units, which could indirectly influence economic growth in the community by establishing significant new business units.

Strengthening Strategic Cooperation and Diversifying Capital Sources for the Successful and Prosperous Village-Owned Enterprise (BUM Desa). The management of the Village-Owned Enterprise (BUM Desa) may establish partnerships with agricultural processing companies and horticultural companies located in the vicinity of Wonosari Village, as well as with other BUM Desa and microfinance institutions, to support the needs of existing business units. Formal Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs) with selected partners shall be drafted, outlining the rights and obligations of each party and precise mechanisms for sharing benefits. The BUM Desa actively seeks information and submits proposals for grants/soft loans from the government, explores investment partnerships with private entities, and explores community-based funding schemes (crowdfunding) based on transparent and participatory business proposals.

Community Empowerment and Enhancing Active Participation in Developing Successful and Prosperous BUM Desa. BUM Desa needs to establish an inclusive BUM Desa

Community Communication Forum and hold quarterly meetings. This forum aims to openly convey information to the community, gather their aspirations, and involve them in the decision-making process related to business units that directly impact their lives. In addition, an Entrepreneurship and Collaborative Skills Training Program should be initiated with a minimum target of 20 participants each year. This program should be implemented in collaboration with relevant agencies, training institutions, and organizations that focus on assisting Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), with training materials tailored to local resource potential and market needs. In terms of recruitment for BUM Desa business units, priority should be given to residents of Wonosari Village who meet the required qualifications, through a clear and transparent recruitment mechanism.

Furthermore, BUM Desa is also encouraged to promote community participation as micro investors, if possible, to strengthen a sense of ownership and community involvement in the development of BUM Desa. Implementing these recommendations requires the design of a conducive communication forum for open and constructive dialogue, as well as the involvement of mentors from various relevant sectors in the training program.

4.6 Factors Influencing the Formulation of BUM Desa Development Policies in Efforts to Improve the Village Economy

The strength of interactions and organizational structures of BUM Desa in formulating BUM Desa development policies to improve the rural economy is greatly influenced by the strength of interactions and internal institutional structures of BUM Desa. As Hall described in Dudley & Richardson (2000) and Dwiyanto (2017), policy changes are characterized by shifts in the dominant paradigm. The paradigm of policy-making actors and the dynamic resource environment fundamentally shape how a policy is formulated and the extent to which its implementation can be successful. In the context of BUM Desa Wonosari, the organizational structure regulated in Village Regulation Number 6 of 2016 (amendment to Number 5 of 2014) clearly defines the key roles in this process: Village Deliberation (MAD), Advisor (Village Head), Operational Executives (Director and staff), and Supervisors (BPD). The Village Deliberation (MAD) is the primary foundation in policy formulation. As a forum involving the BPD, the Village Government, and community elements, MAD serves as an arena for reaching strategic agreements, including the establishment of BUM Desa, the formation of managers, capital approval, and the determination of the Articles of Association/Bylaws (AD/ART). This consensus-building process ensures that the policies produced reflect the collective needs and aspirations of the community, thereby granting them strong legitimacy from the outset.

The Village-Owned Enterprise Advisor, the Village Head, is crucial in providing advice, consideration, and

supervision. Article 13 of Wonosari Village Regulation Number 6 of 2016 explicitly regulates the Village Head's obligation to supervise the implementation of activities and protect the Village-Owned Enterprise from potential performance decline. The interaction between the Advisor and the Operational Implementer enables strategic control and ensures that policies are implemented in line with the village development vision. The Operational Implementer, led by the Director of the BUM Desa, is the spearhead of policy implementation. Their obligations to execute, develop, identify economic potential, and collaborate with other economic institutions demonstrate a proactive role in translating policies into concrete programs. Article 23 of the Wonosari Village Regulation emphasizes the importance of cooperation with other BUM Desa or third parties (private sector) based on the principle of mutual benefit. This indicates that BUM Desa policies are internally oriented and encourage external networking and collaboration to expand economic reach and impact. The medium-term plan of BUM Desa Sukses Makmur to build a mini-market to accommodate local SME products is a concrete example of how the Operational Manager's vision aligns with community needs and is accommodated within the policy framework.

Meanwhile, the Supervisor, appointed by the Village Consultative Body (BPD), is vital as a control and representative of the community. Article 17 of the Wonosari Village Regulation emphasizes the Supervisor's obligation to hold general meetings to discuss the performance of the BUM Desa and the authority to consult on business development activities. Interaction between the Supervisor and other BUM Desa components ensures that policies remain relevant to community needs and accountable. Additionally, issues related to Access to Capital: Limited capital and difficulties in accessing formal loans are classic challenges for BUM Desa. Policies must seek innovative solutions to overcome these barriers through strategic partnerships, sustainable financing schemes, or asset guarantees. Taxes or Levies on BUM Desa: The potential imposition of various types of taxes and levies requires clear fiscal incentive policies. These incentives are important to reduce operational costs, promote growth, and increase investment, especially for small businesses in rural areas. Policies must ensure alignment between BUM Desa and tax/levy authorities.

Strengthening the Institutional Framework of BUM Desa: The legal status of BUM Desa, mandated by the Job Creation Law and registered with the Ministry of Law and Human Rights, is a significant step in strengthening the position of BUM Desa as a trusted and indissoluble business entity. Policies should leverage this status to build investor and partner confidence. Business Judgment Rules (BJR): The issue of BJR provides legal protection for BUM Desa managers from claims arising from business losses, provided they act within the mandate of the Village Assembly and with good intentions. Policies must establish clear boundaries for

BJR to encourage bold yet accountable decision-making. Transformation of BUM Desa: The government has prioritized BUM Desa, including its allocation to the Village Fund. Policies must encourage managers to pursue targeted village empowerment seriously. Plans to add business units such as mini-markets to accommodate local SME products are concrete examples of transformation that policies need to accommodate and support. Integration and Regulation Updates: Village regulations need to be adjusted to follow up on Permendes No. 3 of 2021 (on Development and Guidance, as well as Procurement of Goods and Services) and the Minister of Village, Development, and Transmigration Decision No. 3 of 2025 (on the use of Village Funds for food security, with at least 20% allocated to this sector). Policies must ensure regulatory harmonization so BUM Desa can operate within a clear legal framework and support government priority programs. In the Dynamics of Environmental Resource Power Changes, the Journey of Successful and Prosperous BUM Desa reflects how environmental resource dynamics, particularly human resources (HR), directly influence policy formulation and implementation. At the beginning of its establishment (2014), BUM Desa policies focused on improving HR through collaboration with Gajayana University in Malang due to a lack of understanding among administrators. This shows that initial policies must be oriented toward basic capacity building.

In the subsequent period (2016–2020), policies developed rapidly with the addition of business units (waste management, savings, and loans) and external collaborations (BNI). This reflects policy adaptation to opportunities and the increasing capabilities of HR. Changes to the Articles of Association and Village Regulations also demonstrate policy flexibility in responding to organizational developments. However, data also indicates a period of stagnation (2022–2024) due to changes in management structure and a lack of internal coordination. Accountability reports that only focus on financial aspects, without routine activity reports, indicate a gap between policies on paper and implementation practices. This stagnation ultimately led to new policies focused on structural improvements, precise task distribution, and adding staff for business units. This indicates that policies must have strong evaluation and adjustment mechanisms to address internal human resource dynamics and leadership challenges. Overall, formulating BUM Desa policies is a dynamic and iterative process. Policies must balance the strength of formal structures with the interaction style between actors, be responsive to community demands and external opportunities, and adapt to critical issues and changes in the resource environment, particularly human resource capacity. Only then can BUM Desa sustainably contribute to improving the village economy.

V. CONCLUSION

Identifying internal and external aspects in the successful and prosperous village-owned enterprise (BUM Desa) Sukses Makmur, based on a SWOT analysis of BUM Desa Sukses Makmur, concludes that this BUM Desa possesses strong foundations for future development. This is evident from its management achievements, diversification of existing business units, experience collaborating with financial institutions, legally recognized legal status, support from the village government, and active community participation. However, the BUM Desa also faces internal weaknesses such as the need to improve human resource competencies, a period of management stagnation, limitations in activity reporting, potential overlap of tasks, dependence on leaders, suboptimal utilization of cooperation opportunities, and instability of management personnel. Externally, BUM Desa has significant opportunities from the potential for integrated marketing development for MSMEs and village products, the need for platforms and training for local MSMEs, the potential for improved governance and utilization of abundant natural resources, the significant human resource potential in the agriculture and livestock sectors, the potential for collaboration with local companies, and the positive trend in the utilization of BUM Desa for local economic empowerment. However, BUM Desa must also be aware of threats such as market price fluctuations, potential competition from other businesses, unfavorable regulatory changes, changes in consumer preferences, limited sustainable support from local companies, limited access to information and technology, and the risk of bad credit.

The strength of interaction and structure within the institutional organization of BUM Desa Sukses Makmur lies in its potential for interaction and institutional governance, particularly through inclusive and transparent village meetings as the highest decision-making forum. The role of the Village Head as Advisor/Commissioner and the Village Council (BPD) as Supervisor also provides potential support from the village government, cooperation with the private sector, and control and channelling of community aspirations. The management of BUM Desa has a proactive mandate to carry out operations and develop BUM Desa. Interaction within the organizational structure needs to continue to adapt to government regulations related to BUM Desa, such as Permendes PD TT No. 3 of 2025 concerning the use of Village Funds for food security.

Formulating strategies and programs for the Sukses Makmur BUM Desa through consideration of resources, the development strategy for the Sukses Makmur BUM Desa was formulated by considering internal and external conditions, resulting in four main approaches. First, leveraging strengths and opportunities for aggressive growth through optimizing natural and human resources, strategic partnerships, empowerment of MSMEs, and developing ecotourism. Second, strengths can be used to mitigate threats

through business unit diversification, institutional strengthening, service quality improvement, product innovation, and the development of cooperation networks. Third, minimizing internal weaknesses and leveraging opportunities through human resource capacity building, establishing transparent governance systems, organizational restructuring, and diversification of capital access. Fourth, minimize weaknesses and avoid threats through human resource stabilization, developing contingency capital plans, evaluating business units, and effective communication. This overall strategy is designed to complement each other and requires commitment and support from all elements of BUM Desa and relevant stakeholders for successful implementation.

Alternative policy recommendations for the development of Sukses Makmur BUM Desa recommend adopting several strategic policies for sustainable development. These include strengthening institutional and financial governance through village deliberations, adopting a digital accounting system, and providing intensive training for financial managers. Investment in developing competent and integrity-driven human resources is also emphasized, with a medium-term human resource development plan, continuous training programs, and a transparent recruitment system. Developing flagship business units based on local potential and food security, strengthening strategic partnerships, diversifying capital sources, empowering the community, and increasing active participation are key priorities to improve Wonosari Village's economy.

The formulation of BUM Desa development policies is a dynamic process strongly influenced by internal interactions and institutional structures. For example, BUM Desa Wonosari demonstrates how the Village Assembly serves as the foundation for policy legitimacy, while the role of the Village Head as Advisor ensures strategic control. Operational Implementers drive implementation by collaborating and developing business units, such as a mini-market development plan for SMEs. Supervisors (Village Development Board) ensure accountability and the relevance of policies to community aspirations. However, BUM Desa policies are not immune to external and internal challenges, such as access to capital, taxation/fee policies that require incentives, the importance of legal entity status for institutional strengthening, legal protection through Business Judgment Rules, the need for business transformation, and the requirement for integration and regulatory updates in line with higher government regulations. This dynamic is evident in the journey of the successful BUM Desa Sukses Makmur, where policies had to adapt from an initial focus on human resource development to expanding business units and eventually facing a period of stagnation that demanded structural improvements. Overall, BUM Desa policies must balance formal governance with effective interaction, responsiveness to needs and opportunities, and adaptability to

critical issues and human resource changes, to become the primary driver of village economies.

Institutional Strengthening and Participation: BUM Desa needs to continue strengthening institutional governance by involving active participation from the community and stakeholders in every decision-making process. This can be done through inclusive and transparent village deliberations and establishing BUM Desa community communication forums. **Human Resource Capacity Building:** Investment in the development of human resources (HR) managing BUM Desa should be a priority. Structured and sustainable training programs need to be designed to improve the competence of managers in various aspects, including modern BUM Desa management, financial management, digital marketing, and business unit development.

Innovation and Business Diversification: BUM Desa are encouraged to continue innovating and diversifying business units based on local potential. Technology and developing strategic partnerships with various parties, including MSMEs, local companies, and financial institutions, can support these diversification efforts. **Financial Transparency and Accountability:** BUM Desa's financial management must be transparent and accountable. Adopting digital accounting systems and regular, easy-to-understand financial reporting can increase public and stakeholder trust. **Strategic Cooperation Development:** BUM Desa needs to build and expand strategic cooperation networks with various parties, including other BUM Desa, local governments, financial institutions, and the private sector. This cooperation can open access to broader resources, markets, and knowledge.

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